

TYPES OF FORM AND MEANING OF ADJECTIVES

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Abstraction: In this article, we will learn about the characteristics of adjective and how adjective is made

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Primarily, it denotes the attribute of partial action by the subject. An adjective, affixed to a noun, delineates its attribute. The notion of an attribute encompasses characteristics such as color, size, shape, disposition, weight, and taste. Adjectives are classified into two categories based on the nature of the attribute: substantive adjectives and relative adjectives.

Substantive adjectives denote the inherent and non-relative, as well as gradable, attributes of the subject: red, yellow, large, small, blue, white.

Relative adjectives specify the attribute concerning some object, characteristic, quantity, location, or action: material necessity, fractured dish, central seat. The distinction between relative adjectives and substantive adjectives lies in the absence of gradation and comparison in the former. Unlike substantive adjectives, relative adjectives cannot indicate degrees of the attribute. While they cannot be attached to verbs, certain adjectives formed with the -iy and -viy suffixes can occasionally be appended to verbs. Adjectives encompass nine semantic categories.

1. Characteristic adjectives indicate the character traits of things; beautiful, cute, indifferent, polite, naughty.

2. Status adjectives; beautiful, rich, poor, ugly, beautiful

3. Formative adjectives; circle, round, flat, oblong

4. Color adjectives; blue, green, yellow, blue, white, black

5. Qualities of taste; salty, tahir, sweet, bitter, sour, sweet

6. Adjectives indicating smell; smelly, stinky, smelly, smelly

7. Positional adjectives; rural, wall, internal, external

8. Quantitative adjectives; wide, narrow, big, huge, long

9. Adjectives indicating time; autumn, winter, morning.

There are four levels of adjective by excess or deficiency of the sign:

Ordinary level; red, white, clean, sweet, beautiful, polite

Comparative degree; bigger, more beautiful, louder, rougher

Advanced degree; very red, extremely beautiful, crimson, full, the most beautiful

Reduction degree; dark, bluish, oozing, bruising, short, a little big

We can form adjectives in two ways: affixation and composition

Affixation method also has many forms of adjective living. We need to use the adjective-forming affixes correctly and appropriately, because they are synonymous.

Noun-li; Kecha bozordan qizil *gulli* ko'ylak oldim (Yesterday I bought a dress with red flowers from the market.)

Noun-dor; Talabalar bugungi yangi mavzudan *xabardormidingiz* (Students, are you aware of today's new topic?)

Ser-noun; Dehqonlar bu yil *serunum* yerlardan juda ham yaxshi hosil olishdi. (Farmers got a very good harvest from serunum lands this year.)

Be-noun; Bugun yegan ovqatlarimning hammasi negadir *bemaza* tuyilyapti. (All the food I ate today seems to be bad for some reason.)

Ba-noun; Inson bilim taraflama *badavlat* bo'lishi kerak. (A person should be rich in knowledge.)

No-noun; *Noto'g'ri* ekanini bilib, yana shu narsani gapirish bu nodonlikdir (Knowing that it is wrong and then saying the same thing again is ignorance).

Adjective-chan; Nigora shu kunlarda juda ham *xayolchan* bo'lib qolgan (Nigora has become very imaginative these days)

Verb-chak/chik/chak; Men shunchalik *qizg'anchiq* qizmanki, xattoki dugonam boshqa qizlar bilan gaplashsa, borib shu qizni o'ldirib qo'ygim keladi (I am such a hot girl that even if my friend talks to other girls, I want to kill her)

Verb-gok/gok; Nasiba juda ham *tirishqoq* qiz, har doim hamma darsga tayyorlanib keladi (Nasiba is a very diligent girl, she always comes prepared for every lesson).

Verbs-ag'on; Maktabimizda *bilag'on* o'quvchilarning soni kundandan- kunga ortib borishi direktorni hursand qilardi (The number of mature students in our school was increasing day by day, making the director happy)

Verb-mon; Diyor juda ham ishni ko'zini biladigan *ishbilarmon* yigit (Diyar is a very good business man)

Verb/imitation+(a)ki(qi)shartaki; Bugungi imtihonlarning hammasi *og'zaki* shaklda bo'ldi (Today's exams were all oral).

Verb--k/-q/-g'; Daryoning suvi shunchalik *tiniq-ki*, unga qarab o'tirsam qalbim orom oladi (The water of the river is so clear that if I sit looking at it, my heart will rest)

Verb-kin-qin-g'in-gun; Nasiba kasallanganligi sababli juda ham *ozg'in* bo'lib qoldi (Nasiba became very thin due to illness.)

Verb-ma; Do'stimning biroz tobi yo'q edi men unga *qaynatma* sho'rva tayyorlab berdim (My friend wasn't feeling well, so I made some soup for him)

Verb-(a)rli; Vaqtimizni *zerikarli* o'tkazmaslik uchun ko'p kitoblar o'qishimiz kerak (We should read a lot of books so that we don't spend our time boring)

Imitation; Ayol *liqildoq* joyga o'tirib manglayini ushlab, og'ir o'yga cho'kdi (The woman sat down in a dark place, holding her handcuffs and deep in thought).

Verb-ch; Har doim yurtimiz *tinch*, osmonimiz musaffo bo'lsin (May our country always be peaceful and our sky clear)

Noun-iy-viy; Maktabdagi *devoriy* jurnallarga yangiliklar kiritishni Azizga toshirdik (We entrusted Aziz with adding news to the school's wall magazines)

noun/walk+gi-ki-qi; Uyimizning *atrofidagi* uylarni juda ham chiroyli qilib bezatibdilar (They decorated the houses around our house very beautifully).

noun-i; Jannat xola *jannati* ayollardan edi (Aunt Jannat was one of the women of Jannat)

Noun/adjective-cha; O'zligimizni yo'qotmaslik uchun *o'zbekcha* milliy liboslar kiyib, Navro'z bayramini yaxshi kayfiyatda o'tkazdik (In order not to lose our identity, we wore Uzbek national costumes and spent the Navruz holiday in a good mood).

adjective-namo; Nasim qilgan ishlaridan *uyalgannamo* holatda do'stining yuziga qaray olmadi (Nasim was ashamed of what he had done and could not look at his friend's face).

noun-simon; Bugun darsda yangicha "*sharsimon*" metodidan foydalanib dars o'tdik (Today, we used the new "spherical" method)

noun-parvar; *Ma'rifatparvar* jadidlarimiz biz uchun yaratgan asarlarni hammamiz o'qib, o'zimizga to'g'ri xulosa chiqarishimiz kerak (We should all read the works that our enlightened ancestors have created for us and draw the right conclusions for ourselves.)

In the method of composition, we can form compound and double adjectives.

noun-noun; Bo'lgan voqealar Karimning *toshbag'ir* bo'lishiga sababchi bo'ldi. The events caused Karim to become stone-faced.

Adjective-noun; Karima shunchalik *oqko'ngil* qiz Karima is such a sweet girl

Noun-Adjective; O'tmishda dilozordan *xudobezor* deb bejizga aytishmagan. In the past, it was not for nothing that they called Dilozor an ungodly person.

Adverb-noun; *Kamhosil* yerlarda nima eksang ham foydasi yo'q. No matter what you plant in the poor lands, it is useless

Adverb-verb; Hozir zamon rivojlandi, *tezyurar* poyezdlar ham insonlarga qulaylik keltirdi. Now the time has developed, high-speed trains have also brought convenience to people.

Verb-verb; Nargiza ko'p ovqat yegani sababli "*yebto'ymas*" laqabini oldi. Nargiza got the nickname "Eatless" because she ate a lot.

Pronoun-noun; Navro'zi ayyom oldi *umumxalq* hasharlari bo'lib o'tdi. Nationwide celebrations took place before Navrozi.

Noun-verb; O'zbekistonda ham *osmono'par* uylar ko'payib ketgan. Skyscrapers have also increased in Uzbekistan

Pronoun-adjective; Nodir o'zbilarmon bo'lgani uchun har doim afsuslanardi. Nadir always regretted being selfish.

Number-noun; Ikkiyuzlamachi insonlarni ko'rsam jirkanaman. I hate hypocrites.

Number-verb; Uning ko'zlari shunchalik qattiq ediki, *beshotardan* otgandek edi. His eyes were so intense that it was like shooting from a gun.

Paired adjectives are pairs of adjectives that can both be used independently: Smart people know how to behave everywhere.

Paired adjectives, some of which are used independently: Nasim, it's better if we stay away from dirty work. Dual adjectives where both parts are not used independently; Grandfather Sabir wished the two young people to be brothers and sisters.

Adjectives also have a genitive feature, in which the noun to which the adjective is attached is dropped.

If you associate with evil, you will die from evil.

Prizes were awarded to the pioneers.

Wisely excellent

The younger ones sat closer to the fire, and the older ones sat further away from the fire.

Adjectives and adjectives must be used without definiteness.

The composition of the lexeme qizg'ish-lexeme, which is similar to the lexeme sarg'ish- in the modern Uzbek language, is originally explained differently: adding the suffix -g'i to the verb lexeme kiz-, which historically means red. The u-adjective lexeme was made and the suffix -sh was added to it, meaning "a little": (qiz-g'u-qizg'u-) - sh -qizg'ush; later it changed to the sounds of i and i: qizhgush- khizghish. Therefore, from the point of view of the modern Uzbek language, the lexeme qizgish is considered to be root: qizgish barg; like branches with a reddish tint. When this affix is added to the lexeme, there is a tight syntagmatic relation between the base and the affix in terms of sound: to the lexeme ending with the phoneme k, the -kim allomorph of this affix is added, to the lexeme ending with the phoneme -q, the allo morpheme -qina is added; therefore, as a result of the syntactic relationship, allophones k, q of the phoneme r occur here, and the phoneme g appears in the form of a g-k-q chain.

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